

Language Resources, Tools and Services in the CESAR Project and META-* Framework

Marko Tadić

Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Zagreb
Ivana Lučića 3, 10000 Zagreb, Croatia
marko.tadic@ffzg.hr

Abstract

The speech gives an overview of the results achieved so far within the ICT-PSP project CESAR. The new or enhanced/enlarged language resources, tools and services were/are made accessible in three batches, so we will briefly describe their contents. The project includes partners from six Central and Southeast European countries and their respective languages while it operates as an integral part of META-NET Europe-wide initiative.